

Short name	NIMBY or not?	Long name	Is 'Not In My Backyard' a useful explanation for public responses to CCUS?
Geographical scope	Most research on public perceptions of CCUS focuses on research in European nations (either single countries or comparative). North American and East Asian nations are also regularly represented in the research literature.		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Several researchers, and industry actors, focused on energy development siting have termed local opposition to energy projects NIMBY – not in my backyard ^{1,2} . Nevertheless, leading scholars in this area recommend against such a simplistic and unnuanced description of differential acceptance levels at local and national scales ³ . People local to a project have more awareness of things that could be threatened (or advanced) through the project – e.g., local tourism, cultural meanings, and job prospects ⁴ . They might also have specific experiences with prior energy development – such as coal mining – which could evoke comparisons to previous industrial problems or accidents, or to loss of trust in industrial and/or government actors that were not good neighbours to local communities ^{5,6} . The reasons for local opposition are often complex, but do mean that context specific understanding is essential for assessing the viability of specific CCUS projects ^{7,8} .		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Industry, government, and public commentary on CCS opposition has not infrequently labelled (and denigrated) public opposition as 'simply' NIMBY sentiments ⁹ . The key point here is that higher levels of opposition for populations close to a project need to be examined in depth to understand why this is, and whether there is prospect to address the public concerns. Dismissing public reactions as NIMBY does little to further the goals or viability of a given CCUS project.		
Other issues this affects	Public support for CCUS, public engagement with CCUS, communication about CCUS, spatial comparisons of CCUS perceptions (e.g., local vs national)		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saito, A., Itaoka, K., & Akai, M. (2019). Those who care about CCS—results from a Japanese survey on public understanding of CCS. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 84, 121-130. • Wojakowski, D., Langhelle, O., Assadi, M., & Nagy, S. (2022, October). Public acceptance of CCS/CCUS technology in onshore areas in NW Poland. In <i>Baltic Carbon Forum</i> (Vol. 1, pp. 16-16). JVE International Ltd. 		

¹ Saito, A., Itaoka, K., & Akai, M. (2019). Those who care about CCS—results from a Japanese survey on public understanding of CCS. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 84, 121-130.

² Wojakowski, D., Langhelle, O., Assadi, M., & Nagy, S. (2022, October). Public acceptance of CCS/CCUS technology in onshore areas in NW Poland. In *Baltic Carbon Forum* (Vol. 1, pp. 16-16). JVE International Ltd.

³ Devine-Wright, P. (2011). Public engagement with large-scale renewable energy technologies: breaking the cycle of NIMBYism. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2(1), 19-26.

⁴ Braun, C. (2017). Not in my backyard: CCS sites and public perception of CCS. *Risk Analysis*, 37(12), 2264-2275.

⁵ Terwel, B. W., & Daamen, D. D. (2012). Initial public reactions to carbon capture and storage (CCS): differentiating general and local views. *Climate Policy*, 12(3), 288-300.

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^[1] Saito, A., Itaoka, K., & Akai, M. (2019). Those who care about CCS—results from a Japanese survey on public understanding of CCS. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 84, 121-130.

^[2] Wojakowski, D., Langhelle, O., Assadi, M., & Nagy, S. (2022, October). Public acceptance of CCS/CCUS technology in onshore areas in NW Poland. In *Baltic Carbon Forum* (Vol. 1, pp. 16-16). JVE International Ltd.

^[3] Devine-Wright, P. (2011). Public engagement with large-scale renewable energy technologies: breaking the cycle of NIMBYism. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2(1), 19-26.

^[4] Braun, C. (2017). Not in my backyard: CCS sites and public perception of CCS. *Risk Analysis*, 37(12), 2264-2275.

^[5] Terwel, B. W., & Daamen, D. D. (2012). Initial public reactions to carbon capture and storage (CCS): differentiating general and local views. *Climate Policy*, 12(3), 288-300.

^[6] Williams, R., Jack, C., Gamboa, D., & Shackley, S. (2021). Decarbonising steel production using CO2 Capture and Storage (CCS): Results of focus group discussions in a Welsh steel-making community. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 104, 103218.

^[7] Bellamy, R. (2022). Mapping public appraisals of carbon dioxide removal. *Global Environmental Change*, 76, 102593.

^[8] Krause, R. M., Carley, S. R., Warren, D. C., Rupp, J. A., & Graham, J. D. (2014). "Not in (or under) my backyard": geographic proximity and public acceptance of carbon capture and storage facilities. *Risk Analysis*, 34(3), 529-540.

^[9] Xenias, D., & Whitmarsh, L. (2018). Carbon capture and storage (CCS) experts' attitudes to and experience with public engagement. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 78, 103-116.